

The Role of Myanmar Women in the Anti-Fascist Resistance Movement

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Abstract

In the early 1942, the Japanese Army and Burma Independence Army (BIA) marched into Myanmar and they successfully drove out the British. During the three years of Japanese rule, Myanmar went through such hardship, suffering the mental agony, they gained many bitter experiences. Under the leadership of the A.F.O all Myanmar patriotic men and women were organized. Many other women were also in the East Asia Youth League and they served the tasks of anti-fascist movements and organized the underground units. Myanmar women played the crucial role in the anti-fascist Japanese movement. Most of the Myanmar women actively participated in the movement of anti-fascist resistance although they were not full time member of any particular associations or parties. They did it because of their patriotic spirit. It is decidedly clear that the Myanmar women participated very actively at the risk of their lives in the resistance.

Key Words: Myanmar Women, Fascists, Japanese Rule, Resistance

Introduction

During the Second World War the Japanese occupied the countries in Southeast Asia with the slogan of “the Great East Asia Co-Prosperity Sphere”. Myanmar fall under the Japanese Military Administration since the Japanese Imperial Army and the Burma Independence Army advanced into and occupy Myanmar in four army columns in February 1942 till March 1945.

On 1 August 1943, Myanmar was made an independent state, but the external relations of the state were entirely in the hands of the Japanese, so that the first action of the new state had to be a declaration of the war against Britain and her allies. A civil administration was organized under the Japanese military administration. Dr Ba Maw was appointed as head of Civil Administration. During the three years of Japanese rule, Myanmar went through such hardship, suffering the mental agony, they gained many bitter experiences.

As a result, a strong anti-fascist sentiment developed in Myanmar and the number of anti-fascist members grew gradually within the East Asia Youth League (Burma), the Burma Army, the People's Revolutionary Party. They organized resistance movements against the Japanese Fascist. In order to get contact with the Allies. The British had by then began their offensive to reclaim Myanmar from the Japanese hands and they realized that they could not regain Myanmar without the help of Myanmar people. They therefore accepted the request of the Myanmar Anti- fascist forces to co-operate with the British to expel the Japanese.

Myanmar patriotic leaders started to organize the resistance forces in 1943, which were then scattered and unorganized. They established contact with the Allied Forces towards the end of 1944. Under the leadership of the A.F.O all Myanmar patriotic men and women were organized. The Communist Party of Burma (CPB) also made contact with Thakin Thein Pe and Thakin Tin Shwe and they also sent secretly the Myanmar patriotic youth to Calcutta.

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There they had to attend a secret military training course. In the middle of 1944, the Allied Powers gained victories, after the opening of a second front. The Myanmar patriots got an opportunity to expel the Japanese. When The Communist Party of Burma sent the patriotic young men to India, Ma Mya Yi from Kyaukse, also went on the hard journey to India in the face of many difficulties and troubles. Before the trip, she organized anti-fascist forces in Kyaukse Township. Moreover, she tried to organize Thakins and comrades. She was given the duties of a woman organizer by Thakin Soe. In spite of her parents' prohibition, she served her duties actively.

Many other women were also in the East Asia Youth league and they served the tasks of anti-fascist movements and organized the underground units. They were Ma Khin Lay and Ma Tin Yi from Yesagyo, Daw Saw Mya from Amarapura, Daw Mya Nu and Thakinma Ma Ohn Khin (the future Boh Kyar's wife). Besides, Ma Hnin Si (a) Daw YiYi from Bago moved actively together with the men in anti-fascist movement organizing underground movements. Daw Saw Mya who was given the duty of organizing the women by Thakin Soe, came to Yangon and attended a political training course for two months. She organized the women in one town after another in the Phyarpon District. The women organizers, who had attended the political training course, became the cadres of the anti-fascist resistance. Multiplier courses were given by the female cadres in all districts of the country. Hence, all of the Myanmar women comrades participated systematically in the anti-fascist resistance.

The force of Myanmar women became an auxiliary force of the Burma Defence Army (B.D.A) as it became necessary to reinforce the B.D.A. A Women Regiment has to be legally formed. Regarding this matter, General Aung San explained that it was not sufficient for Myanmar women to carry out only Ba La Nga Dan and that the forming of a regiment of women was absolutely and urgently needed. General Aung San added that both the Russian women of the Soviet Union and the Chinese women of the Chinese Communist Party actively participated in the struggle for their national liberations.

Daw Saw Mya was given the duty of forming the Women's Regiment by general Aung San. Thus she went to Colonel Zeya of the War Office, and discussed the programme of forming the Women Regiment. Firstly, Daw Khin Kyi Kyi from Phyarpon, Ma Hla Khin (the future colonel Ye Htut's wife), Ma Khin Htar Htar and Ma Khin Ohn Yin (the future teacher of North Okkalar) were also invited. Captain Kyaw Thaug (the future Colonel Kyaw Thaug), who was Superintendent of the Women's Regiment and Captain Toe Lwin, gave the women comrades the necessary military training. They also studied the tactics of espionage. Commander-in-Chief General Aung San signed the declaration for the organization of the women's Regiment and announced it as the notification No. 8 on 7 February 1945. This showed that Myanmar women have equal rights and opportunities with men in Myanmar society.

At the beginning, the Women Regiment had only five members and Daw Saw Mya was appointed as an officer commander. In a short time, the number of female comrades grew rapidly up to a hundred. Most of them were teenagers and very enthusiastic to fight for the country's independence. The first centre of the Women Regiment was located at Naypyidaw Transportation building on Inya Kyetkyun. That building was a place for organizing the women and performing the tasks of anti-fascist movements.

The Allied Forces No. 224 and 136 counter-attacked the Japanese forces in Myanmar in February 1945. Victories were achieved on every front. The time was ripe for A.F.O to openly resist the fascist Japanese. Therefore, the leaders of A.F.O, held a meeting at General Aung San's residence in Natmauk Road in Yangon from 1st to 3rd March 1945. They divided the

country into seven regional commands and Rakhine division, Upper Myanmar division and Yangon division. Moreover, the female comrades were assigned different duties in the respective divisions. Daw Saw Mya, Ma Khin Htar Htar, Ma Kyi Nyunt (the future Editor of Naingnganthit U Than Nyunt's wife), Ma Hlaing Hlaing (the future Captain Yan Aung's wife), Ma Mya Win (a) Daw htay from Letswechaung village of Danubyu Township were given duties in No. 7 Regional Command. The female organizers, Ma Khin Kyi, Ma Than Than, Ma Ohn Yin, Ma Nu Nu and Ma Khin Tint were given duties in No. 4 Regional Command, and Ma Hla Khin and Ma Khin Kyi were also given duties in No. 6 Regional Command. They went to their respective divisions and distributed pamphlets and collected information regarding Japanese forces.

During the period of preparation for resistance, Ma Ohn Kyi from Taikkyi Township distributed pamphlets for resistance in Okkan village. Before starting the resistance, they had contact with the Allied Forces No. 136 in India. Ma Khin Kyi Kyi wrote the telegraph in English and she translated the book on guerrilla warfare written in English into Myanmar. During the period of resistance, the female comrades gathered information regarding the Japanese troops, supplied food for revolutionaries and cooked food for resistance regiments. They took care of the wounded. There were many female comrades, who were obliged to obtain information from the Japanese forces. Ma Ni Ni from Kyaukphyu Township (the future teacher of a nursery school at Tharkata), was given duty of collecting intelligence on the Japanese forces by the Allied forces. She went along with the male comrades and crossed the Rakhine Yoma at the risk of her life. Moreover, the female comrades secretly carried the weapons for guerrilla warfare and kept them secretly in haystacks.

There were many nurses who took care of the injured comrades even in the face of dangerous attacks by Japanese soldiers. Daw Khin Aye and Naw Asme, the nurses of Pynmanar Military Hospital, kindly took care of the wounded. Thakinma Ma Ohn Khin from Yenangyaung, who did not have sufficient money to send supplies to the revolutionaries' camp, sold the gold coins, which she got from the Allied forces. When the Japanese Kampeitai got that clue and traced her, she evaded to other places. Even though medicines and medical equipment were not sufficient in the hospital, Daw Khin Kyi (General Aung San's wife) and Daw Khin Gyi (Thakin Than Tun's wife), the nurses of Rangon General Hospital, gave medical treatment to the best of their ability to the comrade patients.

Similarly, in Pyay district, where the Japanese Kampeitai were searching for Burma Army in the Towns and villages the soldiers disguised themselves as villagers and ladies pretended that they were their husbands. In this way, Myanmar ladies also played a role in protecting the revolutionaries. It demonstrates that, the Myanmar women participated very actively at the risk of their lives in the resistance of Japanese fascists. The Myanmar women throughout the country including farmers, workers, shopkeepers, teachers, doctors, nurses, etc. from all classes of Myanmar society helped the Resistance in diverse way. For instance, the young men U Ba Kywe, Ko Thaung Nyaunt and Ko Bo Shein from Linzin, Sagaing gathered information about the camp of Japanese forces and their arsenals. They then stole the small weapons and bombs from the Japanese arsenal of Butarhaung and Ngartutgyi bazaar. Daw Pon and Daw Chon the hawkers of vegetables concealed those weapons to the secret camp of revolutionaries at Ahnauntkon village.

In this way, under the leadership of A.F.O and the Burma Army, the Myanmar people co-operated with the Allied forces and they drove out the Japanese troops. By 30th April 1945, the Japanese Army had withdrawn from Yangon completely. Indeed, as the Japanese Army withdrew from Myanmar, they also killed many civilians and destroyed many towns and villages. In Bago district, female youth joined the fighting. They attacked Japanese ships and

dispersed the boats. The Burma Army raided the Japanese military building. In Phyarpon district a lady, Ma Mya Shin, transported bombs and guns from Phyarpon to Byu village in the proximity of the Japanese stockade. It is a land mark in history in making contacts with the Allied forces, organizing for underground units, collection and concealing the weapons and the food supplies, giving medical treatment to the patients etc. Most of the activities of Myanmar women were more effective than men's activities in carrying out the anti-fascist Japanese movement.

Conclusion

The Myanmar women played the crucial role in the anti-fascist Japanese movement. Most of the Myanmar women actively participated in the movement of anti-fascist resistance although they were not full time member of any particular associations or parties. They did it because of their patriotic spirit. It is decidedly clear that the Myanmar women participated very actively at the risk of their lives in the resistance. The Myanmar women during the anti-fascist resistance were able to sustain the character, the morale and the fighting spirit of the Myanmar people. They contributed social services voluntarily. They were also actively involved in the resistance under the banner of the A.F.P.F.L. They sacrificed their lives for Myanmar. After the war the Myanmar women continued to be active in the struggle for independence under the guidance of A.F.P.F.L.

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Daw Hnin Mya

Executive Members of Women Congress

Daw Khin Gyi

Daw Khin Kyi

Ten Divisions' Military Map

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Personal Interview

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